

The Procedure For Equipping The Biology Room In General Secondary Schools

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Abstract: *The introduction of the continuous education system in our republic, the study and dissemination of best practices in higher education institutions of developed countries, the introduction of innovative and information technologies into the educational process, the organization of the educational process, in particular ,along with formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications and professional-pedagogical competences in students, the theory of revision of the problem of formation and development of special competences related to the base and science is required.*

Keywords — Education, scientific-theoretical, biology, biological competence, didactic tools.

INTRODUCTION.

On October 8, 2019, in order to implement reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan in all spheres, including the education system, which is considered a priority sphere in the social sphere, on October 8, 2019, the PF "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" - Decree No. 5847 was adopted. (National database of legal documents, 09.10.2019, No. 06/19/5847/3887). This concept clearly shows the directions of reforms in the higher education system.

An innovative approach to teaching requires students to acquire not only the knowledge, skills and abilities standardized by DTS, but also general, basic and special competencies related to science.

The implementation of the competence approach in teaching is the following factors:

1. A high level of scientific-theoretical, pedagogical-psychological, scientific-methodical training of the teacher, acquisition of modern thinking skills, appropriate and appropriate use of innovative and information technologies in the educational process;

2. The ability of the teacher to determine ways to introduce innovations in order to ensure the integrity of educational content, teaching methods, tools and forms;

3. Mutual cooperation between the teacher and students to achieve identical educational goals according to B. Blum's taxonomy;

4. In order to determine the effectiveness of the educational process, the use of standard and non-standard educational and test tasks in monitoring and evaluating the acquired

knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, as well as general and private biological competence (ability);

5. Determining ways to use interactive methods and information technology products, taking into account the specific features of the stages of formation of biological knowledge among students;

6. In order to strengthen the material and technical base of teaching biology, enrich it with electronic textbooks, multimedia, animated presentations, control and training programs, virtual laboratories that are products of information technologies, and use them in their place. determined by the fact that it has been launched.

Based on the innovative approach to biology, it is assumed that teaching will be carried out in two different directions:

1. Use of achievements and innovations in the field of biological science and technology in updating the content of biological education.

2. Use of innovative and information technologies in biological education.

An example of innovation in updating the content of biological education is the creation of electronic textbooks, virtual laboratories, and target groups, which incorporate animation, multimedia, and the use of innovative and information technologies in the second direction of biology classes.

Teaching biology based on an innovative approach is carried out in the following stages:

1. The initial stage - innovative and information technologies are analyzed by the biology teacher. Using them, training programs are designed.

2. The intermediate stage - training developments developed with the use of innovative and information technologies are conducted pedagogical experience - testing.

3. The final stage - pedagogical experience - the results of the test are analyzed, training developments that have prepared the ground for achieving the intended goal are popularized.

In accordance with the goals and tasks of the teaching process of biology based on the innovative approach, introducing innovations to the educational content, teaching methods and tools, the organization of the educational process through the teacher's pedagogical activities, innovative and as a result of being managed through information technologies, a guarantee of achieving the intended result is considered.

In order to improve biology education in the conditions of the state and social orders placed before the higher education system, as well as the innovative approach to teaching, it is necessary to implement the following:

- Teaching biology based on an innovative approach, using innovative teaching tools, methods and forms in lectures, laboratory, practical and seminar classes, independent education and work outside the auditorium;

- Teaching biology on the basis of an innovative approach, organizing and managing students' cognitive activities according to the purpose, determining the means and methods of activating this activity, ways of developing learning motives;

- An innovative approach to biology is based on focusing on practical issues, students' academic, practical and work, creative and independent thinking skills, conscious attitude to the environment. rish, implementation of the professional direction of biology education;

- composition of qualification requirements, professional-pedagogical, general and biological competence (ability) specified in the DTS of biology in the environment of innovative approach;

- Diversification of control types in the teaching of biology on the basis of an innovative approach, establishing the use of standard and non-standard educational tasks, that is, through the rating system of the level of students' mastery of knowledge, skills and abilities. it is necessary to solve problems such as regular control, making appropriate changes to the teaching process according to the obtained results.

It is known that today's science and technology have developed rapidly and the flow of information has become global, the amount of knowledge accumulated by mankind is so unlimited that, at the same time, the ability of a person to fully master all these sciences is limited. In accordance with the specialization, interests, needs and aspirations of a person, the ground is created for their formation as a person and the development of natural-scientific literacy. Laws of nature and society are analyzed on the basis of a person's natural-scientific

literacy, they become beliefs, a clear vision of the world around us, knowledge of the development of the organic world based on certain laws, professional activity, perception of problematic situations that arise in nature and society, expert and society as a socially active citizen, it will be possible for him to develop alternative options for solving them.

In the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the clear goals for the fundamental increase in the welfare of the population and the improvement of the quality of life, the comprehensive and rapid development of society and the state, the modernization of the country and the liberalization of all spheres of life determined.

The experience of the educational system of the developed countries of the world shows that the continuous implementation of innovations that ensure quality growth in this system, like in all areas, has become the driving force of society and economic development.

Uzbekistan has set the path of a rapidly developing country with a stable market economy with a high share of innovation and intellectual contribution in production, a competitive industry in the modern and global market, as well as a favorable investment and business environment.

In the teaching of biology based on an innovative approach, lectures and seminars are organized from modules, local-level Keys stage, Venn diagram, chain of terms, biological dictation, didactic game technology at a special methodical level, modular educational technology, cooperative game was organized using teaching technologies. These technologies make students the subjects of their educational activities and create a subject-subject relationship in pedagogical relations.

In order to increase the efficiency of the educational process and to strengthen the educational motivation of students, attention was paid to the level of difficulty of the control tasks in determining the acquired knowledge, skills, qualifications, support and private competencies in science, in particular, reproductive, productive, partially research and creative level questions and test tasks were used. The types of control have been diversified, that is, self-control through adaptive test tasks of students, mutual control during work in small groups, and teacher control are used.

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